

STUDENTS' OPINIONS ON THE EFFECTS OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES ON OPTIONAL MODULES

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Abstract. *This research paper explores the opinions of students about the effectiveness of educational technology for their studies of optional modules. To have a better understanding of how technologies influence understanding of optional modules, attention was paid to benefits, challenges, and students' opinions on implementing them. The data was collected by using a questionnaire. The study demonstrated that educational technologies have several benefits for boosting the quality of education, despite some disadvantages in implementation. In conclusion, further research is recommended for a better understanding of integration issues.*

Keywords: *educational technology, students' opinions, optional modules, academic performance, university students.*

1. Introduction

1.1 Background Information

Over time, digital technologies have different effects on students' education and its quality. This highlights the importance of the correlation between innovations and learning systems. Educational technologies have improved students' understanding of subjects by providing opportunities and a more comfortable environment for their studies (Bereczki & Kárpáti, 2021; Cabaleiro-Cerviño & Vera, 2020; Henderson et al., 2017; Vitoria et al., 2018). However, the implementation of these technologies requires new teaching methodologies, which result in challenges for both teachers and students (Henderson et al., 2017; Bereczki and Kárpáti, 2021).

1.2 Specific Information

Technologies have influenced different fields of study, such as finance, economics, law, programming, and business (Grabińska et al., 2021; Sandybayev, 2020; Vitoria et al., 2018). Now, most universities present information interactively, using e-boards, projectors, and graphs. This approach enables students to enhance their understanding and engagement in the study (Cabaleiro-Cerviño & Vera, 2020). On the other hand, the technology integration has changed teachers' roles in this process, shifting their responsibilities more to instructing rather than educating (Cabaleiro-Cerviño & Vera, 2020; Sandybayev, 2020).

1.3 Aim

This study will examine students' perceptions on the importance of educational technologies for their academic performance at the Westminster International University in Tashkent (WIUT). This research also aims to investigate the role of educational technology in students' understanding of optional modules by considering the benefits and challenges of educational technology for their studies.

1.4 Scope

This research paper explains the opinions of the university students about opportunities provided by educational technologies. The information is beneficial for both students, educators and WIUT administration due to providing insights about possible technology implementations. We studied the CIFS level students' opinions of WIUT and received 52 responses.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Educational technologies play a significant role both for students and teachers (Cabaleiro-Cerviño & Vera, 2020; Henderson et al., 2017; Sandybayev, 2020; Vitoria et al., 2018). The implementation of technologies enhances students' engagement in the learning process and provides additional opportunity for improving the understanding of the studies (Cabaleiro-Cerviño & Vera, 2020; Henderson et al., 2017; Stosic, 2015; Vitoria et al., 2018). In this literature review, the implementation of educational technologies for improving studying and teaching, its influence on understanding optional modules, and teachers' beliefs about the role of technologies will be covered.

2.2 Implementing Educational Technologies to Enhance Teaching and Learning

The implementation of educational technologies beneficially influences learners' educational performance and productivity. For example, educational technologies have several advantages to improve the quality of education by increasing students' involvement, positively affecting information reception, expediting the recognition process, and boosting understanding of material (Cabaleiro-Cerviño & Vera, 2020; Henderson et al., 2017; Vitoria et al., 2018). However, Henderson et al. (2017) found that varying considerably on institution, subject disciplines, and study levels, educational technologies have been proved inconsistent.

Smart learning environments and various technology-based approaches can facilitate the learning process. A number of studies highlight the use of educational technology as helpful for students due to allowing them to have independent access to multimedia materials, diagrams, and video lectures (Cabaleiro-Cerviño & Vera, 2020; Vitoria et al., 2018). Nevertheless, Sandybayev (2020) stated that digital technologies for learning are not able to fully replace traditional education because the role of educational technology is to change the interaction between teacher and student. Furthermore, educational technologies are useful to collect and evaluate information more effectively, as well as to develop creative thinking, collaborations, and communication skills (Bereczki & Kárpáti, 2021; Omirzak et al., 2022). Meanwhile, the research conducted by Henderson et al. (2017) suggests that the belief about students being digitally adapted is inaccurate.

2.3 Influence of Educational Technologies on Optional Modules

Studies show that educational technologies have impacted different fields of study. According to Grabińska et al. (2021), it is essential to integrate innovations in accounting and finance fields. Artificial Intelligence aspects, such as automation, biometrics, and cybersecurity surveillance should be taught at universities, leading to new changes in these fields. Meanwhile, in business classes, Sandybayev (2020) states that e-learning is more efficient than traditional educational practices. Moreover, to enhance students' motivation and willingness to work, platforms such as YouTube could facilitate a collaborative approach to learning through gaming (Sandybayev, 2020; Vitoria et al., 2018).

Technologies, particularly Blackboard Learn, increase students' interest, and motivate them to achieve higher results. Interaction is a key factor in e-learning that boosts the teaching and learning environment (Sandybayev, 2020). Additionally, Vitoria et al. (2018) suggest updating the development of e-education with the latest trends.

2.4 Teachers' Beliefs about the Role of Educational Technologies

The integration of educational technologies has led to different outcomes. Some studies have shown technologies as beneficial instruments, increasing students' productivity and results (Bereczki & Kárpáti, 2021; Cabaleiro-Cerviño & Vera, 2020), while others have revealed negative effects such as disruption and suppression of thinking (Bereczki & Kárpáti, 2021) or were unsure about the significance of technologies on education (Sandybayev, 2020). According to Bereczki and Kárpáti (2021), some studies explored teachers' beliefs that supported the concept of technology as a tool to improve students' creativity. Similarly, Cabaleiro-Cerviño and Vera (2020) found that e-learning expanded opportunities for students, which resulted in an increase in the quality of education. However, the findings by Sandybayev (2020) revealed that the main aspect of education was the learning outcomes of students, their abilities, understanding of the concepts, and knowledge, not the teaching methods and implementations of technologies.

Since technologies were integrated into education, they created new opportunities for students, which changed traditional ways of learning. Now, we can see that most university assignments are completed online, through different websites or applications, resulting in an improved learning process (Khanlarian & Singh, 2015). Additionally, the research by Stosic (2015) showcased that the application of educational technologies enabled students to follow their own pace of studying, repeat materials, watch online lessons for better understanding, and receive immediate feedback through performing tests. Together, these findings suggest that technologies positively impacted the process of education. Furthermore, Cabaleiro-Cerviño and Vera (2020) highlighted that educational technologies influenced teachers' roles and responsibilities and reduced classroom constraints.

The implementation of technologies has changed the role of a teacher. Teachers used to be seen as the sole source of knowledge; however, now they have the responsibilities of a facilitator (Cabaleiro-Cerviño & Vera, 2020). As per Sandybayev (2020), teacher responsibilities shifted to instruction and motivation, helping with the organization of studies, and resolving detected gaps, whereas students are now required to be more involved in the learning process, work with data, and develop skills for practical implementation.

2.5 Conclusion

The review of the existing literature demonstrated that digital technologies, depending on students' educational level and ability to apply them in their studies, have a positive impact on education. Also, educational technologies beneficially influence financial and business fields of study through engaging learning. Additionally, the literature review showed teachers' beliefs that the implementation of educational technologies has different effects on students' performance. Nevertheless, a significant gap exists in WIUT students' attitudes toward educational technologies' impact on the academic environment. As a result, this research explores WIUT students' opinions about the impact of how educational technologies influence understanding of optional modules.

3. Method

3.1 Overview

The main purpose of this section is to address the information about research participants, also provide information on how ethical considerations were followed and which research instrument was used.

3.2 Research Participants

In this research, the participants were CIFS level students of WIUT. The number of male participants was 31 (59.6%), while the number of female students who participated in this research was 21 (40.4%), consequently the total number of participants was 52.

3.3 Ethical Considerations

In the description part of the questionnaire, the participants were made aware of the aim of study and informed that all personal information would be kept anonymous. The questionnaire was developed by avoiding questions which could cause confusion or discomfort for participants.

3.4 Research Instrument

The quantitative research method was chosen for this study. The questionnaire was created in Google Forms and consisted of a description and 10 questions to gather necessary data for a deeper understanding of the research question. The types of questions used in the questionnaire were 3 demographic questions, 2 yes-no questions, 1 Likert scale question, 3 mixed type questions, and 1 open-ended. To distribute the questionnaire, several Telegram groups were used. For developing questionnaire questions, ChatGPT was used. For the literature review part, Poe AI tool was implemented to identify possible themes. The questionnaire was chosen since the aim of the study was to explore the perceptions of CIFS students on different optional modules. This approach enabled the collection of a larger size of data from various optional module students.

4. Results

4.1 Overview

The current research was conducted with 52 respondents to investigate students' perceptions on developing academic performance with educational technologies. The results section presents the most useful educational technologies, situations in which educational technologies were helpful, and challenges faced by students in integrating the educational technologies for their studies.

4.2 Students Perspectives on the Effectiveness of Educational Technologies

Table 1. Perceptions about the Helpfulness of Educational Technologies

Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
25%	36.5%	34.6%	1.9%	1.9%

Table 1 provides information about students' perceptions on the statement "Educational technologies at WIUT have been helpful for a better understanding of my optional modules". For the purposes of this data set, student responses were classified into five levels of agreement. What stands out is that the percentage of people who agree (36.5%) and were neutral (34.6%) was almost the same. The next most common option was strongly agree, chosen by a quarter of the respondents (25%). Only 3.8% of participants disagreed with this statement.

4.3 Most Helpful Digital Tool for Understanding Optional Modules

Table 2. Most Useful Technology for Understanding Optional Modules

Computer	Wi-Fi	Turnitin	E-boards	Others
23.1%	55.8%	3.8%	11.5%	5.8%

The students were asked to comment on the helpfulness of technologies for their optional modules (See Table 2). The data illustrates the most used educational technologies at WIUT. Wi-

Fi and computers were the most popular choices. To exemplify, more than half of the respondents (55.8%) chose Wi-Fi as most beneficial for their studies, making it the most preferred technology for education. Computers were ranked second, receiving nearly a quarter of the votes (23.1%), twice as many as chose E-board (11.5%). Lastly, a small percentage of participants (9.6%) selected Turnitin, Intranet, and other learning tools.

4.4 Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of Educational Technologies

Table 3. Issues Associated with Using Educational Technologies

Struggle to adapt to the studies	Internet connection issues	Difficulties with access	Distractions while using	Others
21.2%	55.8%	44.2%	21.2%	3.8%

Students were asked to give their opinions about the challenges they encountered during the learning process while using educational technologies (See Table 3). The most frequently cited issue by students was *internet connection* problems. More than half of all respondents (55.8%) reported this challenge. Moreover, *difficulties with access* was chosen by 44.2% of respondents. *Struggling to adapt to the studies* and *distractions while using* were reported as equally important issues, at 21.2% for both options. Other specific problems were mentioned by 3.8% of respondents.

4.5 Effective Use of Educational Technologies in Varied Situations

Table 4. Beneficial Application of Educational Technologies in Different Situations

Group presentation	Completing coursework	Developing writing skills	Others
50%	65.4%	30.8%	1.9%

According to results shown in Table 4, students found educational technologies most beneficial in completing courseworks (65.4%). Also, the usefulness of digital technologies can be observed in the group presentations; half of all respondents chose it for its helpfulness (50%). Furthermore, 30.8% of participants used technologies for developing their writing skills.

4.6 Students Recommendations for Enhancing Educational Technologies

Table 5. Suggestions for Improving Educational Technologies Provided by Students

Improvements	Example	n =	Percentage
Access	More access to computers, more printers, make database easier to access	10	19.2%
Internet connection	Provide faster wi-fi, better level of internet	6	11.5%
Technological integration	Create more interactive activities, having quizzes in mobile app	5	9.6%
Tutorials	More tutorials and materials for visual programming module implement educational technologies	4	7.7%
Modernization	Smartboards for seminars, adaptive learning platforms, better interface and	9	17.3%

	design		
No suggestions	Everything is great, no suggestions	18	34.6%

Finally, the study has shown participants' suggestions on which aspects of educational technologies could be improved to help them to develop a better understanding of optional modules (See Table 5). In summary, among 52 participants, 34.6% provided no suggestions for the improvement of educational technologies, as they claimed they were satisfied with the current level of technological facility on the campus. Meanwhile, suggestions on providing better access to educational technologies and their modernizations were the most common responses, at 19.2% and 17.3%, respectively. Responses in this category included expanding computer labs, improving access to databases, and providing more printers. Moreover, 11.5% of respondents suggested improving Wi-Fi related infrastructure to have a better internet connection. In addition, a small proportion of students (9.6%) suggested that integrations of educational technologies and more detailed tutorials (7.7%) on digital technology usage would be relevant in the case of WIUT. For instance, having more quizzes in seminars and teaching students how to implement technologies in their studies were some of the cited answers.

4.7 Conclusion

In conclusion, all students shared their opinion of using educational technologies for their studies. Factors such as accessibility, integration, and modernization of educational technologies were stated.

5. Discussion

5.1 Overview

This section summarizes, interprets, and compares the main findings of primary and secondary research papers. We also listed the limitations of this research paper to ensure that further investigations will be more accurate. After data from the questionnaire was collected, benefits and challenges of using educational technologies were identified.

5.2 Perceptions about the Helpfulness of Educational Technologies

According to this research, most of the CIFS WIUT students accept that educational technologies help them to improve understanding of optional modules, as they boost productivity and efficiency. Similarly, studies by Cabaleiro-Cerviño and Vera (2020), Henderson et al. (2017), and Vitoria et al. (2018) show the same findings. For example, technologies increase students' engagement and improve their learning process. Overall, we can see that educational technologies positively influence studying. It can be explained by benefits provided by technologies. They enhance studying and provide extra opportunities for revising materials and independent development.

5.3 Educational technology application problems

Henderson et al. (2017) showed that students are not proficient and comfortable using technologies. Additionally, Berezki and Kárpáti (2021) found that technologies negatively influenced cognitive processes. The present survey reveals that despite the usefulness of educational technologies, some students struggle to adapt to them and even are distracted while using them. These findings confirm technologies being not fully consistent and uncertainty about their significance.

5.4 Most Useful Technology for Study Process

Students found educational technologies mostly useful in completing courseworks and group presentations. It can be associated with benefits technologies provide. With their help,

students have access to various data, which can enhance their knowledge and understanding of the concepts, and they can utilize the digital tools for their presentations, such as e-boards, projectors, and presentation-making programs, which make them more engaged and interested in the process. The same findings are revealed in studies by Cabaleiro-Cerviño and Vera (2020), Stosic (2015), and Vitoria et al. (2018), who showed that technologies stimulate creativity, improve the recognition process, increase the productivity of learning, and develop communication and collaborative skills.

5.5 Limitations and Further Research

Overall, the research was set up appropriately considering all essential factors and elements, but some barriers were faced. Firstly, to obtain more precise information, the number of participants must be expanded. A wide range of experience in different optional modules would demonstrate more accurate data and would allow for deeper investigations. Future studies on similar research issues could be more detailed and relevant for future conditions.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

The research aimed to identify the perception of CIFS WIUT students about the effectiveness of educational technologies for enhancing academic performance. By analyzing the answers of students from the questionnaire, it has been confirmed that the main drawback of using educational technologies is distractions. Additionally, students have problems with the implementation of those technologies due to the lack of experience and understanding. However, integration of educational technology positively affects information perception and provides the opportunity to revise material and lecturer recordings independently. In addition, students find educational technology beneficial for group tasks and presentation preparations. Based on this finding, students find educational technologies positively influencing their academic level, despite some downsides of integrating them.

The findings of this investigation have several significant implications for future development of quality education. To address the issue of the low level of students understanding of how to effectively apply educational technology for studies, administration and lecturers could organize special seminars or tutorials to familiarize students with educational technologies. According to questionnaire responses, it is essential to solve this problem in the future and conduct further research about effective technology integration.

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